

openlaws

Deliverable 4.4.d1

Overview on scientific publications

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1 Executive Summary

OpenLaws is an ambitious legal information project that builds on open data, open innovation and open source software. OpenLaws will help you find legal information more easily, organize it the way you want and share it with others. The Internet platform is adding a “social layer” to the existing “institutional layer” of legal information systems. Together with the different stakeholders, we will create a network between legislation, case law, legal literature and legal experts - both on a national and a European level, leading to better access to legal information. The openlaws core team will also create a “BOLD“ Vision 2020 about what Big Open Legal Data (BOLD) can do in the future and propose a roadmap to the European Commission.

This report gives a short overview of all scientific publications produced during and immediately after the end of the project.

2 List of Publications

1. Dini, P. and Kioupkiolis, A. (2014). Community Currencies as Laboratories of Institutional Learning: Emergence of Governance through the Mediation of Social Value, *Inaugural WINIR Conference*, Greenwich, London, UK, 11-14
2. Lampoltshammer, Th. & Wass, C. (2014). EU Project openlaws.eu. *CeDEM2015*.
3. Littera, G, Sartori, L., Dini, P. and Antoniadis, P (submitted). From an Idea to a Scalable Working Model: Merging Economic Benefits with Social Values in Sardex. Under review with the *International Journal of Community Currency Research*
4. Littera, G., Sartori, L., Dini, P. and Antoniadis, P. (2014). From an Idea to a Scalable Working Model: Merging Economic Benefits with Social Values in Sardex, *Inaugural WINIR Conference*, Greenwich, London, 11-14
5. Marsden, C. (2013). Twenty Years of the Public Interest: Big Open Legal Data. *Law via the Internet Conference*, September 26-27.
6. Salamanca, O. & Eechoud, M. van (2014). Open Legal Data for Europe. Workshop report. 7 pages.
7. Sartori, L and Dini, P (submitted). Sardex, from complementary currency to institution: A micro-macro case study. Under review with *Stato e Mercato*.
8. Wass, C. (2015). OpenLaws.eu - Stakeholder Framework. *Proceedings of IRIS 2015*. Feb 2015, Salzburg, pp.
9. Wass, C. & Lampoltshammer, Th. (2015). Europäische Schnittstellen zur Rechtsinformation. *Souhrada Festschrift*, 8 pages.
10. Wass, C., Sageder, C. & Lampoltshammer, Th. (2015). openlaws.eu – Offene Rechtsinformation. *OGD DACHLI OpenX*, 3 pages.
11. Wass, C. & Lampoltshammer, Th. (2014). Neue Standards für Gesetze und Entscheidungen: ECLI und ELI. *Jus IT 4/2014*, p. 155.
12. Wass, C. (2013). Open Data as an Opportunity for Legal Information Services. *Proceedings of the 16th International Legal Informatics Symposium IRIS 2013*. 21-23 Feb. 2013, Salzburg, Austria.
13. Wass, C., Dini, P., Eiser, T., Heistracher, Th., Lampoltshammer, Th., Marcon, G., Sageder, Ch., Tsiavos, P., Winkels, R. (2013). OpenLaws.eu. *Proceedings of the 16th International Legal Informatics Symposium IRIS 2013*. 21-23 Feb. 2013, Salzburg, Austria.
14. Winkels, R. (in press). Exploiting the Web of Law. Post-proceedings of *Complexité et politiques publiques*, France.
15. Winkels, R. and Boer, A. (submitted). “May it please the lawyer”: A Recommender System for the Legal Domain. Submitted to RecSys 2016, Boston, 2016.
16. Winkels, R. and Boer, A. (2016). Two Experiments in Finding Relevant Case Law. Accepted for *First Conference on Empirical Legal Studies in Europe (CELSE2016)*, Amsterdam, June 21-22, 2016.
17. Winkels, R. (2016). A Hybrid Method for Finding Relevant Case Law. *Proceedings of IRIS 2016*. Feb 2016, Salzburg.
18. Winkels, R. (2015). Experiments in finding relevant case law. *Pre-Proceedings of NAIL 2015*. Dec 2015, Braga.
19. Winkels, R. (2015). The OpenLaws project: Big Open Legal Data. *Proceedings of IRIS 2015*. Feb 2015, Salzburg, pp. 189-196.
20. Winkels, R., Boer, A., Vredebregt, B. & Someren, A. van (2014). Towards a Legal Recommender System. In R. Hoekstra (ed). *JURIX 2014: The Twenty-Seventh International Conference. Volume*

271 of Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence and Applications, IOS Press, Amsterdam, pp. 169-178.
Best Paper Award.